

ИЗУЧЕНИЕ ВЛИЯНИЯ ЛЕКАРСТВЕННОЙ ФОРМЫ КАК ФАРМАЦЕВТИЧЕСКОГО ФАКТОРА НА ТЕРАПЕВТИЧЕСКУЮ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТЬ ЛЕКАРСТВЕННЫХ ПРЕПАРАТОВ**Бандалиева А.А.***Азербайджанский медицинский университет,
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кафедра технологии и управления фармацией***THE INFLUENCE OF THE PHARMACEUTICAL FACTOR IN DOSAGE FORMS ON THE THERAPEUTIC EFFECTIVENESS OF DRUGS****Bandaliyeva A.,***Azerbaijan Medical University, Department of Pharmaceutical Technology and Management***Muslimzade S.,***Azerbaijan Medical University, Department of Pharmaceutical Technology and Management***Aslanov M.,***Azerbaijan Medical University, Department of Pharmaceutical Technology and Management***Huseynova A.***Azerbaijan Medical University,**Department of Pharmaceutical Technology and Management, Senior Lecturer***Аннотация**

Основной целью биофармации является изучение значимых фармацевтических факторов. Среди этих факторов особую роль играет форма, в которой приготовлен лекарственный препарат, поскольку она оказывает значительное влияние на его терапевтическую эффективность. В этом контексте изучение данного влияния является одной из актуальных и важных задач фармацевтической технологии. Рассматривая лекарственные формы с точки зрения биофармации, необходимо применять новые критерии их классификации. С этой точки зрения классификация лекарственных форм с учетом способа введения является более целесообразной, так как метод введения определяет возможный транспорт вещества в организме, а также позволяет проводить сравнительное исследование биоэффективности лекарственных форм.

Abstract

The primary goal of biopharmaceutics is to study significant pharmaceutical factors. Among these factors, the form in which drugs are prepared plays a crucial role in ensuring their high therapeutic effectiveness. From this perspective, studying these effects is currently one of the most important and relevant issues in the field of pharmaceutical technology. When considering dosage forms from a biopharmaceutical standpoint, it is necessary to apply new criteria for their classification. In this regard, classification based on the route of administration is more appropriate, as the method of administration determines the possible transport of the substance within the body and enables a comparative study of the bioeffectiveness of dosage forms.

Ключевые слова: биофармация, лекарственное вещество, лекарственная форма, терапевтический, фармакокинетика.

Keywords: biopharmaceutics, drug substance, dosage form, therapeutic, pharmacokinetics.

In the modern era, several directions of biopharmaceutical research have been identified, including the study of the role of pharmaceutical factors, absorption conditions, biotransformation, biological affinity and its determination methods, the development of methods for identifying drugs in biological fluids, the study of drug pharmacokinetics, and the determination of clinical effects.

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cial role in ensuring their high therapeutic effectiveness. From this perspective, studying these effects is currently one of the most important and relevant issues in the field of pharmaceutical technology. Considering this relevance, we set out to study the biopharmaceutical aspects of drug dosage forms and their constituent drug substances. To achieve this goal, we conducted several studies.

During our research, we first determined that the therapeutic or prophylactic activity of any drug substance is explained by its chemical structure and physi-

cochemical properties. However, the therapeutic activity of the substance is significantly influenced by the "secondary" properties acquired through targeted technological interventions during drug formulation. For example, changes in particle size, combination with excipients, and the development of an optimal dosage form.

The physical properties of the drug substance, the technological processes affecting the properties of the drug substance during formulation, and the excipients included in the dosage form are referred to in the literature as "pharmaceutical factors." From a biopharmaceutical perspective, studying these factors is essential, as they influence the dynamics of drug substances, affect drug stability during storage, and impact many other important parameters.

Throughout human history, drug therapy has held a leading role in the treatment of diseases. Physicians have used various dosage forms in their daily practice, including tablets, ointments, suppositories, and others. However, for a long time, the focus in drug development, production, and prescription was placed not on the dosage form as a pharmacostructural unit but on the active pharmaceutical ingredient (API) and its dosage. The selection of excipients, dosage forms, and formulation technologies was considered a secondary factor that had no significant impact on the treatment process. The dosage form was mainly discussed in terms of its ability to protect the drug substance and ensure its delivery to the site of absorption. Pharmaceutical technology was primarily concerned with developing dosage forms that could maintain their properties over a certain period.

Research and testing were conducted mainly on properties and functions of dosage forms considered decisive based on official pharmaceutical specifications, including:

- The stability of the drug substance within the developed dosage form, despite accompanying challenges (ease of use, dosage accuracy, appearance, smell, taste);
- Economic properties (compactness, transportability, storage conditions);
- Destruction characteristics (disintegration, complete deformation, etc.).

At that time, the identification and quantification of drug substances in pharmaceutical formulations were considered the main priorities.

However, the discovery of the biological role of pharmaceutical factors, the dependence of drug pharmacokinetics on these factors, and the phenomenon of therapeutic non-equivalence in drugs led to the recognition of the dosage form as the fundamental structural unit in pharmacy. This realization necessitated a reassessment of its significance. Experimental and clinical studies have demonstrated that the dosage form plays a crucial role in determining the absorption rate and concentration of the drug substance in biological fluids, directly influencing its effectiveness.

For example, the concentration of spironolactone in biological fluids, when administered in oral dosage forms (tablets, capsules, dragees, granules) at the same dose, varies between 0.06 and 3.75 mcg/L, despite

these forms fully complying with pharmacopoeial requirements (disintegration, mechanical strength, color, appearance, uniformity of content, etc.). Unfortunately, pharmacopoeial standards do not currently account for bioequivalence as a parameter dependent on the type of dosage form.

Biopharmaceutical research has demonstrated that not only the therapeutic efficacy of a drug substance but also the occurrence of adverse reactions in the body upon administration is significantly influenced by the type of dosage form. In many cases, changing the dosage form has been sufficient to eliminate adverse effects and achieve the desired therapeutic outcome.

For instance, long-term therapy with indomethacin suppositories provides effective treatment with minimal side effects, whereas the use of indomethacin tablets often leads to adverse effects such as headaches, dizziness, drowsiness, nausea, vomiting, appetite disturbances, and even ulcers and bleeding in the gastrointestinal tract. Similarly, adverse reactions have been observed with some oral dosage forms containing cardiac glycosides, whereas injections and suppositories can eliminate these negative reactions entirely.

The impact of dosage form selection on the therapeutic efficacy of a drug substance must be studied in modern biopharmaceutics without disregarding other objective properties of drugs. The investigation of dosage forms and their effects remains an essential and urgent area of research.

A dosage form is a convenient form of drug administration and storage that ensures the optimal therapeutic effect of the active substance with minimal adverse effects from a pharmaceutical standpoint.

According to this definition, the primary task in the development and production of a dosage form is to create optimal conditions for the release and subsequent absorption of the active substance. All other requirements of the dosage form are subordinate to these conditions. The new interpretation of dosage forms establishes their pharmacotherapeutic role, preventing arbitrary substitution or empirical selection.

From a biopharmaceutical perspective, new classification criteria for dosage forms are necessary. The classification based on the route of administration is more appropriate, as it determines the potential transport of the substance within the body and enables comparative studies of the bioeffectiveness of different dosage forms.

For example, comparing different ophthalmic dosage forms containing the same active ingredient—eye drops, eye ointments, and ocular drug films—it becomes evident that the major drawback of drops and ointments is their lower therapeutic effectiveness compared to films. The necessary therapeutic concentration is maintained for 20 minutes with drops, 50 minutes with ointments, and 24-48 hours with ocular films. Drops must be applied 12 times per day, ointments 6-8 times per day, while films are required only once per day. Additionally, after applying drops or ointments, an initial overdose is possible within the first few minutes, followed by the removal of up to 80% of the active substance from the eye surface.

When using ocular drug films, their dissolution rate in tear fluid is regulated by using a triblock copolymer as a carrier. Additionally, these drug forms have different characteristics in terms of treatment course frequency, storage duration, and other parameters. Despite having the same route of administration, their manufacturing methods, or more precisely, their technologies, differ.

The classification of drug forms based on technological parameters appears less attractive from the perspective of comparing their therapeutic effectiveness. For instance, grouping pressed suppositories and tablets together because they are produced using similar technologies (from granulated material or powder) may seem logical. However, due to differences in administration routes, they exhibit entirely different absorption rates and concentration profiles in the body.

For example, when using pressed suppositories, after their disintegration in the rectum, the active substance bypasses the liver and other digestive barriers, directly entering the systemic circulation, where it can be detected in biological fluids within five minutes. In contrast, when a tablet is ingested, a complex process occurs involving various factors, including the diffusion of the released drug substance through the stomach or intestines. Once absorbed, the substance enters the liver's portal system. During its passage through the gastrointestinal tract, it undergoes chemical interactions with enzymes, gastric juice, bile, pancreatic secretions, and other digestive components.

From a biopharmaceutical and clinical perspective, attention is given to different administration routes and the varying conditions under which a drug substance moves through the body. For this reason, ointments, suppositories, and other soft drug forms classified based on their aggregate state can be grouped together.

Essentially, with the emergence of biopharmaceutics, dosage forms have transitioned from being studied as a commodity classification to being considered a structural unit of pharmacotherapy. Only those dosage forms that pass bioavailability (bioequivalence) tests receive approval for production.

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